

CRE-AI-TIVE.

Creatives in the Age of AI

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*Polish Designers, Architects, Fashion Creators, Musicians
and Game Developers in the Midst of the Artificial Intelligence Revolution*

CENTRUM CYFROWE

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Introduction

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Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming the foundations of the global creative industries, prompting a profound reshaping of creative processes, business models and professional roles. Once perceived as a futuristic concept straight out of Stanisław Lem’s novels, technology has now become a tangible reality, its deployment being a complex journey, provoking both enthusiasm and unease. On the one hand, AI serves as a powerful driver of innovation, unlocking new creative and operational possibilities. On the other, its adoption faces numerous legal, ethical, economic and cultural hurdles that generate legitimate concerns and hinder its full-scale integration.

This report offers an in-depth analysis of this phenomenon within the context of Poland’s creative industries. Drawing on extensive desk research, a quantitative survey, as well as twenty-three in-depth interviews with experts from the fields of fashion, architecture, design, gaming and music, we aim to synthesise practitioners’ views and attitudes in order to understand the dual nature of AI more clearly. AI is presented here both as an accelerator of innovation and efficiency, and as a source of complex challenges.

In Poland, as in other European nations, the growing significance of artificial intelligence is accompanied by the absence of a coherent national development strategy and appropriate regulation – a concern frequently voiced by professionals across the creative sector. During the course of this study, work was underway on a national AI strategy; however, given the technology’s rapid evolution, the resulting framework may soon prove inadequate. Designers and creators repeatedly draw attention to the lack of clear and accessible legal and ethical guidelines governing the use of existing works in AI model training. Current regulations remain vague, and thus often disregarded in practice, creating a legal “grey area” and highlighting the urgent need to strengthen competencies in this domain. The fast pace of technological change also exposes a wider skills gap:

as many as 53% of design professionals identify AI as the most pressing area for training, underlining the shortcomings of formal education in this regard¹.

The aim of this report is not only to diagnose the current state of affairs, but also to highlight the opportunities that AI presents to Polish creators and to define the essential conditions for its responsible implementation within the creative sector. We explore how artificial intelligence is becoming a genuine partner in the creative process, supporting idea generation and prototyping, and transforming business models through automation and personalisation. These advantages are balanced against legitimate concerns regarding the homogenisation (or “flattening”, “averaging”) of culture, the protection of intellectual property and changes within the labour market.

Through an analysis of selected examples of AI applications in the creative industries, supported by both qualitative and quantitative research, as well as a review of relevant public policies, we aim to formulate a set of comprehensive recommendations. We believe that a conscious and strategic approach to artificial intelligence, grounded in education, cross-sector collaboration and the establishment of clear legal and ethical frameworks, will enable Poland’s creative industries not only to address forthcoming challenges, but also to fully harness the potential of this transformative technology to strengthen their position, including internationally.

It is worth noting that, in preparing this report, we ourselves made use of AI tools. We do so on the principle that any use of AI in creative or analytical work should be openly acknowledged. What remains an open question, however, is the extent to which such use ought to be disclosed. Should, for instance,

1 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, “Zaprojektować polski design. Aktualny stan sektora w Polsce”, maj 2025, https://drive.google.com/file/d/1v4_sukmKnnUWenhGRHByWh6evlIQFhzx/view [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

the use of a search engine such as Google, which itself relies on AI, also be declared? In our case, the situation is relatively clear. We used AI tools for interview transcription (HappyScribe) and for interview analysis (NotebookLM), although this process was complemented by manual coding. NotebookLM also assisted us in drafting this text and in analysing the substantial body of materials collected during desk research, including interviews, reports and datasets. Gemini was employed during the initial editing phase, while the final editing and proofreading were carried out by human editors. Any errors, omissions or inadvertent oversights remain entirely our responsibility. Nevertheless, every effort has been made to ensure that all sources, including data, reports and cited insights and conclusions, are fully and accurately referenced in the footnotes.

1

Methodology

The study was conducted in four stages. First, we carried out desk research, examining how AI is being applied within the creative industries both globally and in Poland. Next, in June and July 2025, we conducted 23 in-depth interviews with Polish artists and, more broadly, with professionals representing various creative sectors. The interviews focused on the following fields: fashion, architecture, design (product and industrial design), music and video games.

At the same time (albeit continuing slightly longer, until August 2025), we conducted a quantitative survey using an online questionnaire addressed to professionals from the same creative fields. The survey contained a combination of closed questions (some single-choice, some multiple-choice, and others using a Likert scale, asking respondents to rate the intensity of a given phenomenon on a 1–5 scale) and open-ended questions. In total, 141 valid responses were collected. The respondent group was not representative, which means its composition does not mirror the actual structure of Poland's creative industries – the proportions of responses from various creative industries do not correspond to the actual share of these industries in the entire creative sector in Poland. For this reason, the study should be regarded as exploratory and comparative in nature, its objective being to identify general attitudes and relationships rather than to measure precise differences between sectors. All responses were processed and analysed to determine the percentage distribution of specific answers. A range of statistical tests was then applied to deepen the analysis and identify relationships and correlations between variables. In analyses examining the use of AI across different respondent characteristics, contingency tables were used (χ^2 , Cramér's V, and standardised residuals). To verify whether there was a relationship between years of professional experience and AI use, we applied Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) and Somers' D coefficient. Spearman's coefficient was also used to test whether declared attitudes towards AI, as well as perceived risks and challenges,

correlated with actual use of AI-based tools. Clusters of consistent attitudes towards AI were identified using factor analysis (PCA method with Varimax rotation).

The research concluded with two exploratory workshops with creators, held on 16 and 17 September 2025 in Warsaw and Łódź, respectively. The first, hosted by the National Film Archive – Audiovisual Institute in Warsaw, brought together participants working in music and gaming. The second, held at Art_Inkubator in Łódź, gathered representatives from architecture, design, and fashion. In total, 17 experts took part in the workshops. The main areas of discussion included legal and ethical issues, the evolving definition of creativity, transformations in the labour market, and the practical applications of available AI tools.

2

AI in the Creative Industries – An Overview of the Ecosystem

Public Policies on the Use of AI in the Creative Sectors

In its report “Zaprojektować polski design” [Designing Polish Design], Creative Industries Development Centre (Centrum Rozwojów Przemysłów Kreatywnych, CRPK; now named Creative Industries Institute – Instytut Przemysłów Kreatywnych) highlights research showing that Poland still lacks a national strategy for developing its design sector – a view shared by 67% of professionals in the field². Among the key challenges facing the Polish product design industry is the growing importance of AI, coupled with the absence of clear regulatory frameworks, an issue noted by 35% of respondents³. Designers point to the lack of legal definitions and ethical standards governing the use of visual materials for AI model training, creating a “grey area” that urgently calls for regulation⁴. In terms of education, respondents emphasise the scarcity of AI-related knowledge gained through formal learning⁵. The report recommends the introduction of educational programmes and training initiatives focused on the conscious and effective use of AI tools, covering both technical and ethical dimensions⁶. Moreover, Poland still lacks a social recognition of “designer” as a figure (there is little shared understanding of the nature, legitimacy and value

2 Ibid., p. 5.

3 Ibid., p. 32.

4 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, “Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą”. Sztuka a sztuczna inteligencja, <https://mintmagazine.pl/artykuly/relacja-miedzy-sztuka-i-artystami-a-sztuczna-inteligencja> [accessed on: 03/10/2025]. It is worth noting that while relevant regulatory frameworks do exist, awareness of them and the willingness to apply them remains limited.

5 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit., p. 67.

6 Ibid., p. 6.

of the design profession)⁷ or of the broader role design plays in the economy and society. This lack of awareness makes it difficult to develop effective systemic measures and targeted support for the sector.

Key public policy recommendations for Poland include:

- 1.** Re-examining and refining the terminology and definitions used to describe the sector, in order to enable more precise and effective support programmes;
- 2.** Raising awareness of the role of designers in society and among decision-makers through information campaigns, meetings and sustained dialogue between the industry and public institutions;
- 3.** Developing and promoting the Polish design brand internationally, through support for exports and protection against foreign competition (including so-called price dumping), by means of quality control mechanisms and preferences for locally designed products;
- 4.** Providing support in the context of AI development, primarily through educational programmes and by strengthening the protection of intellectual property rights;
- 5.** Stimulating collaboration between the design sector and industry, for example through grants that reward the strategic involvement of designers; and
- 6.** Revising design education curricula to align them with market needs, integrating technological, legal, business and AI-related components.

⁷ Ibid., p. 9. As the report observes: "In Poland, there is no social figure of the designer – this was one of the first observations voiced by professionals in the design sector. This statement carries a surprising depth; it reflects not only a lack of understanding of the role design plays in shaping products and services, but also a lack of awareness of the sector's latent potential and emerging trends, and the limited maturity of collaboration between large enterprises, designers, craftspeople and innovators. The report by CRPK seeks to give these professionals a voice and to portray the environment in which they operate."

The Policy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence in Poland from 2020⁸, adopted by the Council of Ministers, sets out the actions to be undertaken and the objectives to be achieved by the Polish government in the short term (by 2023), medium term (by 2027) and long term (after 2027). These measures are designed to foster the development of Polish society, the economy and scientific research in the field of artificial intelligence. The document makes only a passing reference to the creative industries, largely acknowledging the need to encourage and promote the use of AI within creative sectors through ongoing programmes that support AI-based artistic creation. Such initiatives include the organisation of exhibitions and competitions, support for the international promotion of Polish artists and the regulation of intellectual property rights for works created with the assistance of AI. Meanwhile, Poland's Digital Transformation Strategy 2035, currently being finalised by the Ministry of Digital Affairs (as of September 2025), identifies the creative industries as one of the key sectors of the national economy, emphasising their cultural and creative significance, particularly within the digital ecosystem. Among its priorities, the strategy highlights the need to strengthen the sector's competencies in the use of emerging technologies⁹.

Public Policies in Europe

At the EU level, the European Commission has been actively engaged in discussions on the use of artificial intelligence within the creative sectors. However, this involvement largely stems from the broad, cross-sectoral scope of existing regulatory

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- 8 Resolution No. 196 of the Council of Ministers of 28 December 2020 establishing the "Policy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence in Poland from 2020", Official Gazette 2021, item 23; see also: <https://www.gov.pl/web/ai/polityka-dla-rozwoju-sztucznej-inteligencji-w-polsce-od-roku-2020> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].
- 9 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Digitalisation Strategy until Poland 2035*, <https://www.gov.pl/web/cyfryzacja/strategia-cyfryzacji-polski-do-2035-roku> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

frameworks (such as the Digital Services Act – DSA, the Digital Markets Act and the AI Act), rather than from policies designed specifically for the sector in question. Nonetheless, the Commission is developing the Apply AI¹⁰ strategy, which aims to promote the adoption of AI technologies across strategic sectors of the European Union, including the creative sector. It has also hosted an expert workshop dedicated to exploring the role of AI within the cultural and creative sectors¹¹. In addition, various European organisations, including EIT Culture & Creativity and Digital Music Europe, play a significant role in shaping this evolving area.

At the European level, the main areas of public policy development aimed at standardising the use of AI in the creative industries revolve around safeguarding the rights of authors and creators. The International Confederation of Societies of Authors and Composers (CISAC) has called for the global protection of creative rights in response to the rapid advancement of AI technologies¹². Within the music industry, record labels and rights holders stress the urgent need for robust copyright rules and effective enforcement mechanisms to counter both piracy and the unauthorised use of music for AI model training¹³. Transparency and content labelling are also key concerns. The sector urges policymakers to require AI developers to maintain and disclose registries of copyrighted materials used in model training, and to clearly label content generated exclusively by AI, ensuring transparency for consumers.

10 European Commission, *Apply AI Strategy – strengthening the AI continent*, https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14625-Apply-AI-Strategy-strengthening-the-AI-continent_en [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

11 Network of European Museum Organisations, *NEMO contributes museum sector perspective to European Commission AI workshop*, <https://www.ne-mo.org/news-events/article/nemo-contributes-museum-sector-perspective-to-european-commission-ai-workshop> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

12 *AI And Music. Market Development Of AI In The Music Sector And Impact On Music Authors And Creators In Germany And France*, A report commissioned by SACEM, GEMA, conducted by Goldmedia, https://www.goldmedia.com/fileadmin/goldmedia/Studie/2023/GEMA-SACEM_AI-and-Music/AI_and_Music_GEMA_SACEM_Goldmedia.pdf [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

13 IFPI, *Global music report 2025*, https://www.ifpi.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/GMR2025_SOTI.pdf [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

The question of establishing a common regulatory framework is also being discussed. The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) emphasises that regulation should promote harmonisation, reducing unnecessary trade barriers to AI-driven innovation while allowing individual countries to protect their data and support their local creative industries¹⁴. Organisations linked to the open access movement, including activists engaged in various dimensions of openness, such as digital tools, cultural accessibility, and open science, are also contributing to this discussion. For instance, the Open Future Foundation, in its reports, explores how generative AI can be used to benefit creators and the public good. In its report “Beyond AI & Copyright”¹⁵, generative AI is described as a new cultural and social technology that carries the risk of concentrating knowledge and weakening institutions traditionally responsible for producing and curating it (such as research centres). This could result in a situation where commercial AI models, trained on selectively curated and opaque datasets, become dominant sources of information, displacing the role of verified, research-based organisations. As a solution, Open Future proposes the development of public AI infrastructures and a redistribution mechanism based on a levy imposed on the producers of commercial AI systems, intended to support artists and creators, cultural institutions, public media and open content platforms.

14 UNCTAD, *Creative economy outlook 2024*, https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/ditctsce2024d2_en.pdf [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

15 Paul Keller, *Beyond AI & Copyright*, <https://openfuture.eu/publication/beyond-ai-and-copyright/> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

Public Policies Worldwide

Around the world, governments are analysing and shaping (or, in some cases, deliberately opting not to shape) the legal environment governing the use of AI in the creative sectors¹⁶. Many countries are introducing initiatives to address the new challenges arising from this technology. For instance, the Republic of Korea is preparing copyright guidelines related to AI, intended to clarify and mitigate legal risks for creators, rights holders and users of AI-generated materials¹⁷. In Slovenia, the Ministry of Culture has launched initiatives to support the fair digital transformation of the cultural and creative industries. These initiatives aim to create new opportunities for small and medium-sized creative enterprises, encourage innovative forms of media and storytelling, promote fair digital remuneration for creators, improve distribution and equitable access to information and content, as well as strengthen the professionalisation and export potential of creative businesses¹⁸. UNCTAD is likewise advocating international cooperation to establish shared principles for the development and use of AI, together with coherent policy and regulatory frameworks¹⁹.

Global Trends and Challenges

Across the globe, governments are actively analysing and shaping innovation ecosystems and legal frameworks for artificial intelligence, recognising its transformative potential while remaining mindful of the risks it presents²⁰. The subject is also

16 IFPI, *Global music report 2025*, op. cit.

17 UNCTAD, *Creative economy outlook 2024*, op. cit., p. 68.

18 Ibid.

19 Ibid., p. 71.

20 Network of European Museum Organisations, *NEMO contributes museum...*, op. cit.

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being widely explored within academic circles. Across the reviewed materials, numerous positive aspects of AI's application in the creative industries have been identified. AI is predominantly seen as a tool that enhances creativity – a co-creation partner designed to augment, rather than replace, human ingenuity²¹. It supports idea generation, prototyping, and the development of creative variations²². Researchers further emphasise AI's contribution to efficiency and automation. AI technologies are reshaping the creative industries by streamlining processes such as design, screenwriting, video rendering, trend forecasting, supply-chain optimisation²³ and customer engagement. For example, companies in the fashion sector use AI to refine patterns, colour palettes and silhouettes for specific audiences, enabling rapid responses to shifting market trends²⁴. This development extends beyond content personalisation to include the broader customisation of products and services tailored to individual consumer needs. Immersive technologies (Extended Reality – XR, encompassing Virtual Reality – VR and Augmented Reality – AR) are also gaining significance. Their expanding use in design, particularly within fashion, facilitates more engaging and interactive customer experiences²⁵.

The rapid development and growing adoption of AI within the creative industries have not been without criticism or concern. Much of the debate centres on issues of homogenisation (the mass standardisation of the creative output) and intellectual property rights. Artists warn of the risk that creative works

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- 21 Zorana Ivcevic, Mike Grandinetti, *Artificial intelligence as a tool for creativity*, "Journal of Creativity" 2024, Vol. 34, Is. 2, 2024, 100079, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jyoc.2024.100079>.
- 22 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit., p. 12.
- 23 Yunus Emre Öztaş, Balca Arda, *Re-evaluating creative labor in the age of artificial intelligence: a qualitative case study of creative workers' perspectives on technological transformation in creative industries*, "AI and Society" 2025, Vol. 40, p. 4119–4130, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-025-02180-6>.
- 24 Francisco Tigre Moura, Chiara Castrucci, Clare Hindley, *Artificial Intelligence Creates Art? An Experimental Investigation of Value and Creativity Perceptions*, "Journal of Creative Behavior" 2023, Vol. 57, Is. 4, p. 534–549, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.600>.
- 25 Market Data Forecast, *Europe Apparel Market*, <https://www.marketdataforecast.com/market-reports/europe-apparel-market> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

may become increasingly uniform, losing artistic individuality and quality, as AI systems tend to rely on patterns and templates. Safeguarding the rights of authors and creators, and securing consent for the use of existing works in AI model training, remain key challenges²⁶.

Further concerns relate to employment and the need for continuous skill development. There is an ongoing discussion about AI's impact on the labour market, including potential job losses in areas that can be easily and cheaply automated, alongside the creation of new roles in AI system development, supervision and verification. A fear of displacement, particularly among entry-level positions, is widespread. There is a growing recognition of the need to reskill and upskill employees²⁷. From this perspective, the very role of the designer is being redefined. Designers are increasingly viewed as curators of creative processes, in which AI undertakes much of the generative or production work, while the human creator is responsible for the selection and integration of the AI-generated output²⁸. Discussions on the role of AI in the creative sectors also highlight the need for international cooperation to develop jointly agreed principles for the growth and use of AI, along with the corresponding policy and regulatory frameworks²⁹.

Participants in our workshops expressed a strong fear of job loss in creative professions, particularly in junior roles. "It's terrifying – I can see the job market shrinking," one participant admitted. At the same time, Poland's AI landscape has its own distinct characteristics. Workshop participants spoke of a certain false modesty and quiet cleverness in the discreet use of AI tools – behaviours that tend to inhibit open dialogue. There is

26 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit., s. 32.

27 Öztaş Yunus Emre, Arda Balca, *Re-evaluating creative labor...*, op. cit.

28 Ibid.

29 UNCTAD, *Creative economy outlook 2024*, op. cit.

a prevailing sense of shame or reluctance to admit to using AI, in contrast to foreign brands, which often present such adoption as a mark of innovation. Although there are emerging local initiatives, such as the Polish language models Bielik and PLLuM, the high subscription costs of advanced tools remain a significant barrier.

Financing Models

An analysis of existing funding mechanisms and tax incentives designed to support the responsible implementation of AI, while minimising the risk of intellectual property infringement, shows that current solutions remain focused largely on regulatory and compensatory approaches, rather than on concrete financial instruments.

Among the proposed models of financial support for creators, several key directions can be identified. First of all, it is suggested that the existing EU funding programmes, which currently support process modernisation, be expanded to include initiatives that help creators and companies adapt to new AI technologies responsibly³⁰. Secondly, a frequently discussed, though not yet implemented, model involves the introduction of a system of compensation and licensing agreements. This model assumes that companies developing generative AI systems should pay creators for the use of their works in the process of training algorithms, which would require close cooperation with collective copyright management organisations. There is also an emphasis on the need to invest in the development of AI tools that assist artists with technical and organisational tasks

30 Czesława Frejlich, *Polish design: a metamorphosis*, <https://www.wipo.int/web/wipo-magazine/articles/polish-design-a-metamorphosis-38570> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

rather than replace their creativity³¹. Thirdly, an ongoing discussion concerns how to ensure that the public value embedded in AI systems (the AI Commons) is fairly shared with those who produce, store and disseminate knowledge³². In this context, it has been proposed to introduce a universal levy on commercial AI systems trained on publicly available resources. The purpose of this levy would be to redirect a portion of revenues to entities that sustain the information ecosystem. Such a redistribution mechanism would seek to prevent the emergence of a new generation of information gatekeepers, while safeguarding the pluralistic and democratic character of the digital public sphere. The final pillar relates to the funding of broad-based education at all levels, designed to equip both society and creators with the knowledge and skills necessary for the informed and ethical use of artificial intelligence.

Examples of Artificial Intelligence Applications in the Creative Sectors

As noted earlier, artificial intelligence is regarded primarily as a tool that supports creativity and co-creation³³, though it naturally extends far beyond these functions. Europe's creative industries, employing over 7.6 million people and generating more than EUR 640 billion in the annual turnover, have been increasingly embracing new technologies³⁴. In design, AI streamlines the prototyping process and enables the rapid generation of multiple variations of a single idea, significantly accelerating

31 Szilvia Ruszev et al., *Shared-Posthuman Imagination: Human-AI Collaboration in Media Creation*, https://eprints.bournemouth.ac.uk/40681/7/10.18746_epxn-da67.pdf [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

32 Paul Keller, *Beyond AI & Copyright*, op. cit.

33 Zorana Ivcevic, Mike Grandinetti, *Artificial intelligence as a tool for creativity*, op.cit.

34 AI And Music. *Market Development of AI...*, op. cit.

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creative workflows. It also allows creators to move beyond habitual thinking patterns, producing unexpected and original concepts that give rise to a new poetics of design³⁵. In the music industry, AI makes it possible to undertake projects that were previously unattainable – from isolating vocals in archival recordings³⁶ and modifying voice timbre, to creating functional remixes. In doing so, AI offers artists a new expressive language, opening pathways to previously unexplored forms of creativity.

AI is also widely used to personalise products and services, becoming a key driver of user engagement across the creative sectors. Since November 2022, following the launch of ChatGPT, there has been a marked increase in AI investment in art and music production. This surge has profoundly influenced not only creative processes, but also the very notion of authorship itself³⁷.

In line with the growing emphasis on environmental sustainability, the European Commission launched the “ReSet the Trend” campaign to combat fast fashion and promote sustainable, circular textile production. Clothing and footwear manufacturers are encouraged to reduce their environmental impact by reworking production methods, updating existing collections and developing new eco-friendly materials.

The rising importance of AI in the creative industries brings both new opportunities and significant regulatory challenges. Key among these are copyright protection and the absence of clear rules regarding consent for the use of existing works in AI model training. In response to these challenges, calls have been made for technology companies to disclose registries of copyrighted

35 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, “Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą”..., op. cit.

36 Katarzyna Garwol, *AI w sztuce – czy artyści będą potrzebni?* Studium na przykładzie opinii studentów kierunku sztuki wizualne Uniwersytetu Rzeszowskiego, „Media i Społeczeństwo” 20(1/1)/2024, p. 209, <http://doi.org/10.5604/01.3001.0054.6523> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

37 Zorana Ivcevic, Mike Grandinetti, *Artificial intelligence as a tool for creativity*, op.cit.

materials used to train their algorithms, as well as to ensure that content generated solely by AI is clearly labelled. These developments are leading to a fundamental transformation in the designer's work, with the role increasingly evolving toward that of a curator or interpreter³⁸.

These global trends are clearly mirrored in Poland's design and fashion sectors. Research indicates that four in ten companies within these industries already employ AI-based solutions³⁹. At the same time, 35% of respondents identify the lack of oversight of AI's growing influence as one of the five greatest challenges facing the sector. Designers express concern not only about the monotony and loss of individuality in creative projects, but also about concept theft, an issue reported by 34% of respondents. In the face of such uncertainty and rapid technological change, there is a strong demand for knowledge. Artificial intelligence ranks first (53%) among the most sought-after areas of training⁴⁰, revealing a skills gap that formal education has yet to address.

5

Sustainable Design

Alongside the response to technological challenges, Polish design is also evolving dynamically within the wider sustainability movement, which takes into account the carbon footprint generated by design practices. This theme is particularly significant in the context of new technologies and their environmental cost. Although 60% of professionals consider this direction important, costs remain a major barrier, with 67% of respondents reporting that clients are unwilling to bear them⁴¹. Another recurring

38 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, "Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą"..., op. cit.

39 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit.

40 Ibid.

41 Ibid.

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issue is greenwashing, namely the creation of a misleading “eco-friendly” image to gain consumer trust without genuine investment in sustainable development, as identified by 62% of respondents⁴². Within this complex landscape, Polish designers are building a competitive advantage based on distinctive strengths. They are increasingly developing efficient and ethical solutions, approaching waste reduction and resource reuse with creativity and innovation. The strength of Polish design lies in its fusion of traditional crafts⁴³, such as weaving, with modern technologies. Projects are often custom-made, reflecting a deep understanding of market trends and consumer needs, while maintaining exceptionally high standards of quality and aesthetics. Handcrafted production and the use of natural, high-quality materials have contributed to growing international recognition for Polish brands, as reflected in the fashion industry’s 2022 value of EUR 10.2 billion, ranking sixth in Europe⁴⁴.

In some circles, artificial intelligence is now seen as a tool that enhances, rather than replaces, human creativity. This approach is evident across many areas of design, from initial concept development to final product realisation.

One of the key applications of artificial intelligence lies in co-creation and automation during the early stages of the design process. Research indicates that tools such as ChatGPT-4 are used by consultants to generate product ideas, draft prototype descriptions, conduct market analyses and develop marketing slogans⁴⁵. A particularly strong example comes from the footwear industry, where AI supports the development of concepts for niche products⁴⁶. Similarly, in the fashion sector, companies

42 Ibid.

43 “Polish Job 2.0” Exhibition at Dutch Design Week, <https://lodzdesign.com/wydarzenia/polish-job-2-0/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

44 Polish Investment and Trade Agency, *The Fashion Sector*, <https://www.trade.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/THE-FASHION-SECTOR-2022.pdf> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

45 Zorana Ivcevic, Mike Grandinetti, *Artificial intelligence as a tool for creativity*, op.cit.

46 Ibid.

employ AI to swiftly adjust patterns, colour palettes and silhouettes to suit specific target groups, enabling rapid responses to evolving market trends. A notable example of strategic collaboration is the partnership between Tommy Hilfiger and IBM⁴⁷, established to integrate AI into the creative design process, particularly in the development of innovative patterns and colour palettes.

Artificial Intelligence and Art

Another rapidly expanding field is the creation of art and AI-generated content. Since the launch of ChatGPT in November 2022, there has been a genuine AI boom, accompanied by a sharp rise in investment in technologies for music and visual art production. Systems such as Creative Adversarial Networks (CAN) can generate “art” by learning from existing styles and then deliberately diverging from established norms in search of novelty⁴⁸. Researchers are also examining how AI creates images, sculptures and interactive installations, opening up new forms of artistic expression.

In practice, Polish artists are already exploring AI’s creative potential with success. For example, artist Janek Simon, in his project “Meta Folklore”⁴⁹, used a GAN model⁵⁰ trained on 12,000 images of human-body sculptures to generate physical 3D models. Simon emphasised that the project was a way to maintain

47 Tommy Hilfiger and IBM team up to harness AI in the creative design process, <https://www.fashionnetwork.com/news/Tommy-hilfiger-and-ibm-team-up-to-harness-ai-in-the-creative-design-process,936528.html> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

48 Ahmed Elgammal et. al., *CAN: Creative Adversarial Networks, Generating „Art” by Learning About Styles and Deviating from Style Norms*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1706.07068> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

49 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, “Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą”..., op. cit.

50 A Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) is a deep learning model that uses two neural networks – a generator and a discriminator – to create new, realistic data. The generator learns to produce fake data samples (like images or text) that are similar to a real dataset, while the discriminator learns to distinguish between the real and the fake data created by the generator.

ethical control over the training data. Similarly, Studio Noviki⁵¹ employs ChatGPT for scriptwriting and Midjourney and Stable Diffusion for creating visual systems. They regard AI as a “creative partner”, whose imperfections and “hallucinations” serve as a source of inspiration. As they explain, working with AI is “like talking to another artist”, enabling them to discover new aesthetics and think beyond conventional frameworks.

Architecture

In the field of architecture, artificial intelligence is becoming an integral part of the design process, opening new possibilities for optimisation, personalisation and sustainable development. Globally, AI is increasingly used as an advanced tool that supports architects at multiple stages of their work, from visualisation and text-based or visual material searches to product substitution. Its role now extends far beyond simple automation, positioning AI as a collaborative partner in the creative process.

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AI enhances design by analysing complex datasets related to aesthetic trends, building regulations, structural efficiency⁵², social, economic and cultural contexts. It enables topology optimisation and urban planning that take into account factors such as sunlight forecasting. Moreover, design processes are increasingly informed by neuroscientific data⁵³, allowing architects to create spaces that promote user well-being. In this context, neuroarchitecture⁵⁴ – a discipline combining neuroscience and design – has been gaining traction. Supported by AI, it facilitates the creation of healthy and productive environments, including high-performance workplaces.

51 Ibid.

52 UNCTAD, *Creative economy outlook 2024*, op. cit.

53 Ibid.

54 Ruth Hynes, Adrian Davidson, *Outlook on Design Trends 2025*, <https://www.jll.com/en-us/insights/market-outlook/global-design-trends> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

This progress is being driven by the widespread adoption of digital technologies. Across Europe, architects are increasingly using advanced tools:

- 33% use rendering software;
- 49% employ 3D printing;
- 9% use laser scanning;
- 24% work with BIM (Building Information Modelling) and parametric design;
- 6% use performance simulation and analysis tools⁵⁵.

Notably, most professionals have learned to use these technologies independently, highlighting the need to modernise formal educational programmes. There is also a growing emphasis on sustainable design. 54% of architects regularly incorporate low-energy principles into their projects⁵⁶. Immersive technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) are being used more frequently, enabling the creation of interactive visualisations for clients⁵⁷.

In Poland, the interior architecture market is developing rapidly, valued at USD 849.19 million in 2023 and projected to grow to USD 905.8 million by 2032, driven primarily by the expansion of cities such as Warsaw, Kraków and Wrocław⁵⁸. The integra-

55 Architects' Council of Europe, *The Architectural Profession in Europe 2022 Sector Study*, <https://ace-cae.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/2022-ACE-Report-EN-1408-1.pdf> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

56 *The ACE publishes the ninth edition of the Sector Study on the state of the architectural profession in Europe*, <https://ace-cae.eu/news/the-ace-publishes-the-ninth-edition-of-the-sector-study-on-the-state-of-the-architectural-profession-in-europe/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

57 Credence Research, *Poland Interior Design Market*, <https://www.credenceresearch.com/report/poland-interior-design-market> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

58 Ibid.

tion of technology within the architecture and construction industries is becoming increasingly visible. Nearly 30% of real estate professionals already use AI, with 38% relying on it daily, particularly through advanced 3D modelling and VR tools used to present projects⁵⁹. Polish companies are also introducing a range of innovative solutions, including smart chairs connected to smartphones⁶⁰, customised mycelium-based acoustic panels and touch-sensitive electric tables designed to enhance comfort and workplace efficiency⁶¹.

Music

The Polish music market is dynamic and expanding, driven primarily by the growth of streaming. In 2023, digital music sales increased by 21%, securing Poland's position among the world's twenty largest music markets. Polish hip-hop has become the dominant genre, while streaming remains the main form of music consumption⁶². Applications of artificial intelligence in music encompass a wide range of processes – from creative work (composing music, generating melodies, harmonies and rhythms) to production (enhancing recording, mixing and mastering workflows), marketing and distribution (identifying trends and personalising content) and improving fan engagement by increasing the effectiveness of artist support systems⁶³.

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59 Ibid.

60 Marek Kępa, *3 Tech-Savvy Polish Furniture Designs for Your Workspace*, <https://culture.pl/en/article/3-tech-savvy-polish-furniture-designs-for-your-workspace> [accessed on: 7.10.2025].

61 Credence Research, *Poland Interior Design Market...*, op. cit.

62 *Meet New Merlin Board Member Irina Lipczyk-Kolakowska (e-muzyka)*, <https://merlinnetwork.org/e-muzykas-irina-lipczyk-kolakowska-discusses-growth-strategy-and-distribution-in-the-polish-and-ukrainian-music-markets/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

63 *AI And Music. Market Development Of AI...*, op. cit.

A groundbreaking example of AI use in practice is “Now & Then” by The Beatles⁶⁴, a collaboration between Universal Music Group and Soundlabs AI. The technology enabled the isolation of John Lennon’s vocals from archival recordings, making it possible to create the band’s final song. This is a model case of the ethical use of AI for creative purposes. Other notable examples include virtual performances, such as those offered by Sony Immersive Music Studios, which has developed a markerless motion-capture technology that allows virtual concerts to be staged anywhere. This innovation has significantly shortened the production cycle, reducing the time from concept to commercial release to just 11 weeks.

However, these opportunities come with serious challenges. Key concerns include copyright protection, unauthorised use of works for AI training and piracy. Organisations such as the International Federation of the Phonographic Industry (IFPI) are calling for regulations to ensure artists’ consent and transparency in training data⁶⁵. There is also growing anxiety over the homogenisation of content by AI through reliance on existing templates. Uncertainty persists as well regarding AI’s impact on employment and fair remuneration for creators.

Video Games

Poland has firmly established itself as a global powerhouse in the video game industry – a sector the dynamic development of which, dating back to the 1980s, shows no signs of slowing down. Over the past five years, the industry’s revenues have in-

64 James Gaunt, *Isolating The Beatles with AI : So easy anyone can do it!*, <https://medium.com/the-shadow-knows/isolating-the-beatles-with-ai-so-easy-anyone-can-do-it-c6c7b1b5cae8> [accessed on: 06/10/2025].

65 IFPI, *Global Music Report 2025*, https://ifpi-website-cms.s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/GMR_2025_State_of_the_Industry_Final_83665b84be.pdf [accessed on: 06/10/2025].

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created by an impressive 250%⁶⁶, with the Polish video game market growing from USD 344 million in 2017 to USD 608 million in 2021. By 2023, approximately 494 game developers and publishers were operating in Poland, employing over 15,200 people and releasing more than 530 titles annually⁶⁷. With the rapid pace of global technological progress, Polish game development studios are increasingly embracing artificial intelligence, bringing with it both vast opportunities and new challenges.

The Polish gaming sector competes on par with leading international studios – often setting new standards – by actively adopting AI and investing in emerging technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR). A particularly striking example of this ambition is a studio co-founded by Nobel laureate Olga Tokarczuk, which received a grant of nearly PLN 17 million (around EUR 4 million)⁶⁸ to develop an innovative AI-driven technology. The project, drawing on research in game studies, psychology and advanced artificial intelligence, aims to create game characters with psychologically coherent personalities, whose decisions stem from their inner motivations and emotional states. This demonstrates a move towards using AI not merely for automation, but to craft deeper and more immersive experiences.

66 PoLAND of IT masters Information hub, *PARP report: Poland's gamedev sector grew by 250% in 5 years*, <https://hub.landofitmasters.pl/en/revenues-of-polands-gamedev-sector-grew-by-250-in-5-years/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

67 Polish Investment and Trade Agency, *Creative Industries Sector. GameDev*, <https://www.paih.gov.pl/wp-content/uploads/2025/08/The-Creative-Industries-Sector-GameDev-2025.pdf> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

68 *Spółka Tokarczuk otrzyma dofinansowanie. Będzie pracować nad technologią do tworzenia gier*, <https://www.money.pl/gospodarka/spolka-tokarczuk-otrzyma-dofinansowanie-bedzie-pracowac-nad-technologie-do-tworzenia-gier-7079071704505280a.html> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

Polish Creators on AI

Poland's contemporary creative sectors are undergoing a profound transformation driven by artificial intelligence – a process that is complex and often met with mixed reactions. Based on the collected materials, we have identified the key factors which, according to our interviewees and survey respondents representing various creative industries, facilitate the use of AI in creative work, as well as the main barriers that hinder its wider adoption.

Artificial intelligence has disrupted creative industries worldwide, triggering a fundamental reconfiguration of creative processes, business models and professional roles. The majority of respondents in our quantitative survey already use AI-based tools in their professional practice (only 14% reported not using them at all). The analysis of in-depth interviews and survey results confirms the dual nature of AI; on the one hand, it acts as a catalyst for innovation and efficiency; on the other, it poses significant ethical, legal, social and economic challenges.

I think artificial intelligence is already being used, but there's still a huge amount of work to be done. Studios that take on this challenge earlier will gain a strong competitive advantage. The key is to learn how to use these tools systematically, rather than relying on scattered elements, as is often the case now. Personally, I plan that once we find time for pre-production and process reflection, we'll look very closely at what's currently possible: which tools to use, how to configure them and how to prompt effectively. It's a completely new area of knowledge, a new skill set that must be learned – even by excellent programmers. Using such models involves a different kind of skill – perhaps even closer to a designer's mindset than a programmer's, as it requires looking from the user's perspective, identifying what is missing and what we aim to achieve. On the other hand, a programmer who sets up such a system effectively may, in a sense, be creating competition for themselves in the workplace. So, looking at our experience and what's happening around us, I feel we're still at a very early stage of adoption. (IDI #1)

The qualitative and quantitative study revealed a distinct duality in attitudes and perceptions of generative artificial intelligence among professionals in the creative sectors. Some respondents expressed strong resistance, highlighting the risk of losing creative agency and the potential dehumanisation of artistic and design professions.

I'm noticing the emergence of new tools – I'm bombarded with ads for them on Instagram and other platforms. There are more and more programmes that, as I've heard from friends or workshop participants, basically start writing music for you. For me, that's already too much interference. It's hard to say whether you're still the author of such a piece. It's no longer like playing an instrument; it's more like outsourcing the work – a bit like the old Dutch painting workshops, where it turned out that the young apprentices were the ones actually painting the master's works. That's why I'm strongly opposed to this approach and know I'll never enter such a world, unless we're talking about tools that emulate something truly unattainable. (IDI #12)

Concerns were also raised by some about job security and the quality of creative output. Others, however, emphasised AI's potential as a tool that enables new forms of expression and broadens creative possibilities. This divide reflects a deeper tension between fears of eroding traditional professional identity and enthusiasm for innovative artistic practices.

I think there's quite a strong divide, and it's definitely controversial. When I talk to friends who are designers, photographers or artists, opinions are very polarised. Some say that artificial intelligence makes no sense at all, that it deprives us of agency, of individuality, of the human side of the profession. But there are also people who believe you can do amazing things with it. It's great that there are creators who know how to use it and are producing brilliant work. (IDI #15)

A New Spectrum of Creative Work

The current phase of AI adaptation within the creative industries is characterised by its growing instrumentalisation. Technology is becoming an integral part of the creative toolkit, delivering tangible benefits on many levels. Moreover, AI's ability to analyse vast datasets allows creators to make more informed strategic decisions based on market trends and audience preferences.

Since I started using artificial intelligence, I've noticed that I've become more productive. The tasks I dislike – the ones I can automate – I now delegate to these tools, and suddenly I have more time as a creator to focus on the things that AI simply can't do. (IDI #15)

Beyond its functional role, AI increasingly serves as an intellectual sparring partner during the conceptual phase. For designers, composers and screenwriters, it has become a means of overcoming creative blocks, capable of generating countless ideas and visual metaphors. In music, algorithms can extract melodic or rhythmic lines from existing compositions or suggest harmonies for written lyrics. In game development, advanced language models act as creative consultants, helping to structure design concepts and identify analogies.

When it comes to the purely musical side of things, I actually have a funny story. We used AI once when we were looking for a drum line for a song and couldn't find the right reference for ages. Eventually, we did, but of course, we couldn't just use the drums from that track. My colleague said, 'Wait, there's a tool that might help.' And sure enough, we used it to extract just the drum track and fit it into our song. That turned out to be the missing piece that allowed us to finish the track. Later, we rewrote the drum line based on that reference, and it really helped. Without it, we probably would've lost the direction we wanted for the song. Tools like that are genuinely brilliant and are well worth using. (IDI #8)

AI tools, often available through freemium or subscription models, have significantly lowered the barrier to entry into professional creative work. They enable individuals without formal artistic or technical training to produce advanced visual and audio projects. This democratisation carries the promise of unlocking vast creative potential previously constrained by the cost of knowledge and software. At the same time, however, it raises legitimate concerns about the mass production of low-quality content, which may devalue professional expertise and contribute to the growing noise within the digital landscape.

Motivations and Benefits: AI as a Partner in Creativity and Operational Processes

The main driving force behind the adoption of artificial intelligence is its expanding role as a partner in the creative process. Contrary to early fears, most designers do not perceive AI as a substitute for human creativity⁶⁹, but as an advanced tool that amplifies and extends it⁷⁰.

While our survey respondents recognise the risks associated with AI, they are equally aware of the opportunities it presents. A majority (over 50%) agree, or strongly agree, that the use of AI leads to faster and higher-quality data analysis (74.5%) and more efficient management and workflow organisation (60.3%). Respondents also report that AI helps reduce creative production costs (62.4%) and significantly accelerates creative work (56.7%). Slightly fewer (46.1%) view AI as a means of achieving results previously considered unattainable (see Chart 1).

69 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit., s. 12.

70 Ibid.

Chart 1. Benefits of using AI-based tools

(To what extent do you agree with the statement?)

Source: survey results (N = 141).

The practical applications of this potential are already evident across creative sectors. In music, AI enables projects that would have been impossible just a decade ago, such as the precise isolation of chosen stems or layers from multitrack recordings (like the aforementioned case of The Beatles and John Lennon’s archival recording⁷¹), subtle voice-timbre modifications, and the creation of functional remixes tailored to specific artistic needs. In design, AI supports deep personalisation and rapid iteration, while in gaming, it assists writers and developers in building psychologically coherent characters.

In this context, the preparation phase of projects received over half (51%) of mentions from respondents asked when they use AI tools. A little over one-third (36%) referred to the creative stage itself, encompassing concept development and variant

71 Matthew Sparkes, *How AI brought John Lennon back to life for the last Beatles song*, <https://www.newscientist.com/article/2399860-how-ai-brought-john-lennon-back-to-life-for-the-last-beatles-song/> [accessed on: 7.10.2025] See also: pp. 25-26 of this report.

creation. AI tools are also commonly employed in communication and promotion (37%), as well as organisation and administration (31%) (see Chart 2).

Chart 2. Project stages in which AI is used

Source: survey results (N = 141).

The most valued feature of AI is its ability to radically accelerate and optimise work. In visual industries such as fashion or graphic design, generative algorithms can compress production cycles that once took weeks into just a few hours. They enable the rapid creation of realistic product visualisations, marketing campaigns and prototypes, tasks that previously required costly photo shoots and extensive post-production. This technology now influences nearly every aspect of business activity in the creative industries examined, from creative development, data analytics and customer service to marketing and successful audience engagement.

Writing, writing, writing – different kinds of texts, especially for workshops or project support, including applications and other documents. ChatGPT is a huge help. Maybe not for writing the ap-

plications themselves, but for organising them more clearly and logically. For example, when planning different workshop programs, I often used it to generate topics that would be interesting for participants and arrange them in a logical order. (IDI #12)

In the video game industry, AI is used to generate temporary graphic assets (placeholders), allowing teams to test mechanics and concepts rapidly without involving specialist artists in the early stages. This acceleration directly translates into lower operational costs, reduces barriers to market entry for small studios and independent creators, as well as enables faster refinement of ideas.

Although still imperfect, AI tools are increasingly viewed as knowledge resources and reference points rather than creative replacements.

I'd like it to stay that way – that we remain the creators, that we're the ones who make things, and the tools are simply there to support us. Like in construction – there are machines that help, but the person doing the work still needs knowledge, skill and experience to understand what they're creating. I hope that's how it stays – that we create and technology simply assists us. (IDI #20)

AI has become a powerful instrument for business optimisation on levels far beyond streamlining the creative production itself. High awareness of its potential among industry professionals encourages rapid adaptation and drives innovation. Artificial intelligence opens the door to greater product personalisation, supported by technologies such as 3D printing. It also fosters the development of key emerging trends, including sustainable and neuroinclusive design (the creation of work and living environments that actively support the full spectrum of human

neurodiversity, guided by principles such as sensory-friendly spaces and inclusive navigation strategies⁷²), enabling creators to respond to global challenges.

	SM	BT	PD	PP	SO
Jul	5	6	7	8	9
	10	11	12	13	14
	15	16	17	18	19
	20	21	22	23	24
	25	26	27	28	29
	30	31	1	2	3
Aug	4	5	6	7	8
	9	10	11	12	13
	14	15	16	17	18
	19	20	21	22	23
	24	25	26	27	28
	29	30	31	1	2
Sep	3	4	5	6	7
	8	9	10	11	12
	13	14	15	16	17
	18	19	20	21	22
	23	24	25	26	27
	28	29	30	1	2
Oct	3	4	5	6	7
	8	9	10	11	12
	13	14	15	16	17
	18	19	20	21	22
	23	24	25	26	27
	28	29	30	31	1
Nov	2	3	4	5	6
	7	8	9	10	11
	12	13	14	15	16
	17	18	19	20	21
	22	23	24	25	26
	27	28	29	30	1
Dec	2	3	4	5	6
	7	8	9	10	11
	12	13	14	15	16
	17	18	19	20	21
	22	23	24	25	26
	27	28	29	30	31

[1970 = 3136] [Next St. This Day in 313]

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Organisations that integrate AI-driven solutions not only keep pace with dynamic change but often set new industry standards, gaining a distinct competitive advantage⁷³. Its accessibility and ease of integration with existing software make AI a natural and increasingly indispensable component of the digital toolkit. Automation of repetitive tasks, advanced data analytics (enabling a better understanding of audiences), and enhanced customer service all translate directly into improved operational efficiency and market reach. Among creative professionals, there is growing recognition that AI can drive innovation, evolve creative solutions and bring meaningful, positive change to the world.

The development of artificial intelligence has had a broadly positive impact on both the labour market and the wider innovation ecosystem. It contributes to talent growth, motivating many individuals to retrain and enter this rapidly evolving field⁷⁴.

No significant differences were observed in the frequency of AI use at different project stages across the creative industries analysed. The most notable (and statistically significant) variations occurred during the preparatory phase of projects and in the organisational and administrative use of AI. However, it is worth emphasizing that even in these instances, the strength of the relationship between a particular creative industry and AI usage remains moderate (or, in the case of organisational and administrative work, approaches weak levels of correlation). Survey data indicate that design professionals are more likely

72 Andrew Biro, "Neuro-Inclusive Design in Architecture", <https://gbdmagazine.com/neuro-inclusive-design-in-architecture/> [accessed on: 03/10/2025].

73 City Hall of Warsaw, *State of Warsaw AI*, <https://biznes.um.warszawa.pl/-/state-of-warsaw-ai> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

74 Ministry of Digital Affairs, *Sztuczna inteligencja a polski rynek pracy – zagrożenie czy szansa?*, <https://ai.gov.pl/aktualnosci/sztuczna-inteligencja-a-polski-rynek-pracy-%E2%80%93-zagrozenie-czy-szansa> [dostęp: 3.10.2025].

than expected to use AI in the preparatory stages of projects, while musicians tend to do so less frequently. Designers also appear to make greater use of AI in organisational and administrative work.

Although no significant relationships (no linear trend) were found between professional experience and the use of AI at different project stages, a general trend can be observed: individuals with the longest professional experience were more likely than other groups to select the response “I do not use AI,” while those with 16–20 years of experience chose this answer less frequently than expected. It was them – creators with 16–20 years of professional experience – who proved to be the most open to AI adoption, using AI-based tools significantly more often than expected, both during the creative stage and for organisational and administrative tasks. At the opposite end of the spectrum were professionals with over 20 years of experience, who reported using AI less frequently than average, particularly in creative and organisational processes. Similar, though weaker, patterns were observed across other stages of work.

Barriers and Challenges: Quality, Competencies and the Homogenisation of Creativity

The rapid development of generative artificial intelligence has exposed a series of deep systemic challenges that call into question the legal, ethical and economic foundations underpinning the creative industries.

One of the most pressing issues concerns the legality of training data. The principal concern lies in the unauthorised use of copyrighted works to train AI models, creating a legal “grey area”⁷⁵. AI systems are trained on billions of images, texts and musical compositions scraped from the internet, often in breach of copyright law and without the consent of or remuneration for creators. This situation, described by some artists as “parasitism” or “theft in velvet gloves”, creates a legal vacuum and undermines the very basis of the copyright system. A large majority of survey respondents (85.8%, with 8.5% undecided) pointed to the uncontrolled use of human creative labour by AI and the insufficient protection of the copyright. They also emphasised that the legal status of works co-created with AI remains ambiguous – who is the author? Who holds the property rights? This uncertainty fuels unfair competition, as commercial entities can generate content without paying licensing fees, directly competing with artists whose work was used to train their systems.

This issue was also strongly echoed during the exploratory workshops we conducted as part of this study. Participants unanimously agreed that “the law is completely behind,” while technology already allows for advanced modification of voice and image. A particular concern was expressed over the pace of legislative work, for instance, efforts by the Polish Society of Authors (ZAiKS) are expected to take as long as five years. “Where will artificial intelligence be in five years? By then, we’ll have to catch up all over again,” noted one of the musicians in Warsaw. This legal gap creates significant uncertainty regarding copyright ownership of AI-generated content. The ongoing debate centres on whether a prompt itself can constitute a basis for copyright protection, and how much human input is required for a work to qualify as authored. The issue was illustrated by a case in which a designer won a competition with a poster created using AI, prompting the question: “Is this still creative work,

75 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, “Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą”..., op. cit.

or merely reproduction?” Across Europe, AI-generated works remain outside the scope of copyright law, raising additional questions around royalties. How to compensate creators whose works were used to train AI models, and how to manage works co-created with the use of AI.

For many creators, the introduction of AI tools provokes a degree of anxiety. Over one-third of survey respondents (36.9%) admitted to fearing the use of AI in their work, while a further 20.6% preferred “not to think about it”. At the same time, most acknowledged that AI is already being used by their collaborators (71.5%), and that they themselves are open to using it in their creative practice (68.0%).

Chart 3. Attitudes toward the use of AI

(Do you agree with the following statements?)

Source: survey results (N = 141).

Many artists fear that excessive reliance on AI may lead to aesthetic homogenisation and the erosion of the human element in culture (a concern shared by 65.9% of respondents). Works generated by algorithms, even when technically correct, often lack the depth, intentionality and emotional resonance that stem from human experience. Such works are frequently described as “generic”, “overly polished” and devoid of the unique imperfections that often define artistic strength.

I'm afraid it's taking away our individual voice. Chat [GPT] and other AI tools make everything so uniform. I still can't trust it enough to generate something and think, 'Okay, that's good'. It's like I just don't trust the quality. I'm suspicious it feels like you can tell it's not authentic. (IDI #7)

Researchers have also warned of a long-term risk of “AI inbreeding”⁷⁶ – a process in which models trained increasingly on AI-generated data begin to replicate the same patterns and errors. This could ultimately lead to creative stagnation and a decline in the overall quality of digital visual culture. In response to this overproduction of mass content, some experts foresee a renewed appreciation for craftsmanship and artistic practices that emphasise human uniqueness. At the same time, many stress that AI should be regarded as an advanced tool rather than a creative partner, rejecting attempts to “humanise” or anthropomorphise it⁷⁷.

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76 Bernard Marr, *Generative AI And The Risk Of Inbreeding*, <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2024/03/28/generative-ai-and-the-risk-of-inbreeding/> [accessed on: 7.10.2025].

77 Tom May, *Design trends for 2025: creative leaders share their vision for the future*, <https://www.creativeboom.com/insight/what-emerging-trends-will-be-big-in-2025-we-asked-creative-leaders-for-their-predictions/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

Chart 4. Risks associated with the use of AI

Source: survey results (N = 141).

The implementation of AI carries serious implications for the structure of employment within the creative industries. A significant majority of respondents (75.2%) pointed to the risk of job displacement resulting from the growing use of AI (Chart 4). Particularly vulnerable are junior positions and roles involving technical or repetitive tasks, which may severely hinder the entry of new generations of creators into the market and disrupt traditional career progression. In the long term, this may result in a polarised labour market, divided between a small group of highly qualified AI creative directors and a broad base of lower-paid ‘tool operators’.

At this point, I'm simply worried about what's happening in professions built around artistic expression. I've heard from people in the gaming industry that only the most experienced, highly skilled artists are being retained. Juniors are rarely hired, and when they are, it's just to correct AI-generated output. Last year, I saw many layoffs in this sector because of such cuts. It's very sad, because developing one's craft as an illustrator or concept artist is a lifelong process – something people have been training for since they first picked up a pencil, and later, a tablet stylus. (IDI #22)

I tend to think that in 10–20 years, 3D artists might no longer be needed, because AI will be capable of generating high-quality, error-free models and creating animations exactly as we expect. I don't think, though, that the whole process can ever happen without a human being involved. Someone will always need to check whether the result makes sense, as hallucinations happen, and their effects can be problematic. The bigger concern is how new people will enter the market. If, in 50 years, all niches are taken over by AI, there'll be no room for juniors. The responsibility will fall on corporations and large studios to create entry-level opportunities, otherwise, the generation that still possesses these skills will eventually disappear, and that would be a serious problem. (IDI #18)

In a broader social context, the unregulated capacity of AI to generate realistic deepfakes poses a growing threat to public trust and can be exploited for disinformation and propaganda purposes.

I mostly feel worried, and it wears me down. My main concern is that very few people actually verify the information generated by ChatGPT or other AI tools. Such content keeps circulating, spreading misinformation, not just in the artistic field, where it's already a big issue, but globally, in matters of history and geopolitics. It's especially visible with generative AI in graphics or video. People

believe these things uncritically. I had to educate my parents about it, and even now they sometimes get fooled. The worst part is that even I sometimes start doubting myself, because once someone edits a piece and removes the errors, it's hard to tell what's real. And then you ask yourself: do I really have to dig through half the internet to verify it? (IDI #23)

Despite its theoretically promising outlook, the path towards the full and responsible implementation of AI remains uneven. A key unresolved question is whether such full integration is even desirable, and what it would mean for different segments of the creative economy. The most pressing concern, raised almost unanimously across the creative community, is the lack of adequate legal regulation, particularly in relation to intellectual property protection⁷⁸. The unauthorised use of copyrighted works to train AI models, without the consent of or compensation for their authors, poses a fundamental threat to the creative ecosystem. Urgent legal frameworks and policy guidelines are needed to safeguard creators' rights within this new technological reality while allowing continued innovation.

The growing importance of AI is widely seen as a civilisational challenge, one that may lead to job losses. In the design industry, 40% of professionals fear layoffs linked to competition from Asia⁷⁹ – a concern indirectly tied to increasing automation.

Is this just people working themselves up? I don't want to sound harsh, but I see panic among very young people – those in their twenties or mid-twenties. It seems they struggle to cope with the fact that in our profession there are ups and downs. One month is good, the next is terrible, and that's just how this life works. (IDI #3)

78 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit., p. 102.

79 Ibid.

Or:

I think many companies are now considering how to use AI to work more efficiently – and, bluntly speaking, to reduce headcount. Several specialisations in video games are especially vulnerable to this kind of automation. (IDI #1)

Equally significant are the artistic and cultural concerns. There is a genuine fear that widespread dependence on the same dominant AI models could lead to aesthetic monotony, repetition of stylistic patterns and the erosion of the uniquely human dimension of creative work⁸⁰. The overproduction of machine-generated content may further drown out authentic creativity, making it harder for audiences to discover it. Increasingly, discussions in the field use the metaphor of “imperfect, hand-made glass” being preferred to a “flawless, machine-made one”, which symbolises resistance to sterile perfection and an affirmation of human imperfection as the true source of artistic value.

Perhaps, as some of the data-processing and similar tasks become easier and cheaper, those whose work cannot be replaced by artificial intelligence will come to be more highly valued. (IDI #9)

I also think there’s a trend towards making one’s work as personal as possible – that only what genuinely comes from the designer truly matters. And I think this authenticity-based approach somewhat diminishes the importance of whether something has been copied, whether a pattern, cut or colour has been replicated or not. What really counts is your own input. (IDI #7)

80 Aleksander Hudzik, Arek Kowalik, “Dziś z AI rozmawia się tak jak z drugim artystą”..., op. cit.

Despite widespread declarations of using AI in preparatory and research processes, creators consistently emphasised the frequent imperfections of current tools, which are not yet reliable enough to be fully trusted, particularly in areas requiring specialised domain expertise. Among respondents, 34.0% identified this as a challenge (while 51.1% disagreed and 12.1% strongly disagreed; see Chart 5).

There are just so many mistakes. It's like raising a child. You have to put in so much effort just to get a reasonably good result that, for now, I have better sources to draw knowledge from. (IDI #2)

I wouldn't say I'm terrified – that's not quite the right word – but I'm approaching it with a certain distance. That probably best captures my attitude for now. Because on the one hand, the definitions and phrases it generates can be really good and well put together; but I've also come across cases where something immediately felt off. I checked, and indeed it was wrong. So yes – distanced is the right word for how I feel about it, at least for now. (IDI #21)

Interestingly, most creators do not perceive the emergence of AI as a threat to the very definition of creativity itself.

I think creativity – for someone like me, raised in the 20th century and already working in this field – used to be associated with personal effort, difficulty, and education. But now, if you have a tool that works in such a way that, without even touching an instrument, you can say, 'Hey, make me this and that kind of song' or even a whole album – because that's already possible – then yes, something has been created. But is that really art, genuine creativity? To me, no. It's like food – an imitation, something that resembles a meal. It works for a moment, but you can't call it truly balanced and nourishing. (IDI #12)

Another major challenge is the skills gap. Formal education systems are struggling to keep pace with the rapid development of technology, leading to a shortage of specialists with sound knowledge of the strategic and ethical use of AI. As a result, these tools are often used superficially, without a deeper understanding of their mechanisms or limitations. 56.7% of respondents indicated that one of the current challenges associated with AI is the lack of sufficient competence to use AI-based tools effectively (Chart 5). Ethical concerns, including bias and discrimination inherited from the datasets used to train AI models, also require continuous oversight and a more informed approach to the selection and deployment of such technologies⁸¹.

Chart 5. Current challenges related to the use of AI

In your opinion, what challenges related to AI does your industry currently face?

Source: survey results (N = 141).

81 Ibid.

Another critical issue is bias and discrimination embedded within AI models. Training data that reflect social stereotypes can lead to biased outputs. For example, if a dataset represents doctors predominantly as white men, the model will replicate this bias, reinforcing harmful assumptions.

Although around 40% of companies report using AI, this often occurs without a coherent strategy. AI tends to be treated as a convenient automation tool rather than as part of a broader strategic framework. Many organisations underestimate its complexity, work with poor-quality training data, or struggle to understand and control advanced algorithms. They prioritise speed and cost reduction, succumbing to the uncritical hype surrounding the technology.

I got a clear mandate from above that we're supposed to use AI because they care about speed. I argued against it. I'm an artist, and it's really important to me that artistic expression remains clear. But we even had to fill out a form to prove how we use AI. [...] Many people at the top glorify it, they believe that anyone not using AI is falling behind. My supervisor even told me directly that my 'weak point' is not using AI. So I asked: does my work differ in quality from those who do? It turned out it doesn't, but not using AI is considered 'outdated'. I got the mandate from above: I have to show proof that I'm using AI. And I've heard the same from others. They don't want to, but they're simply ordered to. (IDI #23)

Significant economic and psychological barriers also persist. Developing advanced proprietary AI models is extremely costly, requiring vast datasets and substantial financial or institutional resources, thus limiting access to this technology. In the context of the Polish creative sector, an additional obstacle may lie in a certain institutional inertia and the focus on other, more pressing social and political issues, which delay meaningful debate and the widespread adoption of AI.

Chart 6. Future challenges related to the use of AI

In your opinion, what will be the biggest AI-related challenges your industry will face in the future?

Source: survey results (N = 141).

When asked about future challenges related to AI (Chart 6), creators most frequently mentioned standardisation and homogenisation of creativity (the “averaging” of aesthetics – 89.3%), authorship and ethical dilemmas surrounding AI-generated works, including deepfakes, plagiarism and the reinforcement of socially harmful narratives (also 89.3%). Another critical issue is copyright infringement (82.5%). The respondents were also worried about the dehumanisation of cultural expression, resulting from art that no longer reflects genuine human emotions, experiences and perspectives (73.1%). These sentiments were also reflected in the interviews.

When I write texts with ChatGPT, I notice that sometimes you don't really have to think or reflect much. And I think that can, to some extent, take away that element of human ingenuity, vision and concept.

(IDI #3)

Respondents also expressed concern that the use of AI could weaken creative skills (76.6%) and reduce employment opportunities in creative professions (76.6%). Finally, access to advanced AI tools is not always equitable. Their high cost risks excluding freelancers and small studios from the market (71.7%).

Concerns and Doubts About the Use of AI

Both the quantitative and qualitative findings reveal that creators hold a range of doubts about the use of AI and the implications of its implementation. Analysis of the survey results indicates that the use of AI-based tools is strongly correlated with respondents' overall attitudes towards AI. The factors most closely associated with adoption include openness to experimentation and awareness that other team members are already using these kinds of tools. A belief in AI's effectiveness as a management and analytical tool is also positively linked to its use. Strong correlations were also observed among respondents who were less likely to agree with statements such as that AI has a negative impact or leads to the decline of creativity. These findings suggest that individuals who embrace AI tend to recognise its practical value and are less influenced by the more pessimistic narratives surrounding its role in the creative process.

However, reflections on the nature of creativity and the artist's role frequently surfaced during the workshops. More and more creators are asking themselves whether they are still 'cre-

ators' in the traditional sense, or rather 'curators' or 'operators' of technology. "I feel like an operator... just as I used to manage an intern's work, now I manage AI," reflected one participant from Łódź. Similar sentiments were voiced by an art director in the gaming industry, who described treating both her team members and AI as resources to be managed. On the one hand, concerns persist about the decline of human creativity and the homogenisation of cultural output; on the other, there is a strong belief that "good creators will always remain irreplaceable". As a counterbalance to machine-made perfection, some predict "a renaissance of craftsmanship", in which human error becomes a valued marker of authenticity. Despite these reservations, AI is commonly viewed as a supportive tool that "massively speeds up work," automates routine tasks and aids personalisation.

According to the quantitative results, most ethical, social and qualitative concerns are only weakly correlated with actual AI use. This suggests that those who prefer "not to think about AI," fear using it, or believe it leads to the erosion of creativity, bias or dependency, are less likely to employ such tools. However, neither lack of competence nor fear of job loss appears to have a statistically significant impact on AI adoption. In other words, professional factors alone do not constitute a major barrier to the use of artificial intelligence.

Ethics, Copyright and Intellectual Property

Our research shows that creators' knowledge of intellectual property in the context of AI varies widely – from complete unawareness to deep familiarity with the topic, including active engagement in current discussions about labelling content

co-created with generative AI and enabling authors to voice their opposition (opt-out) to the use of their works for training purposes.

Intellectual property... I give up. I'd honestly love to hear from lawyers or IP specialists, because this seems like an incredibly complex issue. (IDI #19)

Exactly. Nobody really knows. My knowledge is limited and I don't fully understand how it works. Is it, as I imagine, that AI takes countless existing patterns and produces some kind of mixture of them all, but with a foundation that's still human, still someone else's authored work? It's like a very elaborate stew made up of all these ingredients, yet ultimately built on other people's labour. Or is it something created entirely out of nothing? I find that hard to believe. There has to be some kind of fuel behind it. As for copyright, honestly, my hand would tremble if I had to sign something major with ZAiKS, like a big hit, confirming that it's mine. I'd be afraid someone could later claim that, by coincidence, it's not fully mine – that a fragment matches their music – and we'd discover we'd used exactly the same bit. (IDI #12)

Minimising the risk of unauthorised use of intellectual property remains one of the greatest challenges. A key demand from creators is the modernisation and harmonisation of copyright law, which currently lags behind technological progress. Respondents emphasised the need for a clear legal definition of works co-created with AI and for explicit rules assigning responsibility for their content and compliance with existing legislation. At present, works generated entirely by AI are not recognised as 'works' under Polish copyright law and may, in principle, be treated as belonging to the public domain. However, interpretations continue to evolve.

I wish these legal matters were sorted out, because right now it looks as though artists are trying to fight for their rights while the owners of the machines aren't interested in any dialogue. They ignore our pleading, because at the moment it feels a bit like Poland in the 1990s – a kind of lawlessness. Grab what you can and run. These companies seem to have adopted that strategy – take everything quietly while it's still possible. Soon, some form of law will appear, and it will be too late. The AI Act already exists, and the Code of Practice is being developed, but for now, these companies just don't care. (IDI #5)

Equally important is the principle of transparency, including both the obligation to label content created with the use of AI and the disclosure of the databases used by technology companies to train their models.

I don't really want to comment on intellectual property, since I feel like I lack the expertise. From the perspective of audiences, users and practitioners working with different kinds of creative works, I'd simply like to see a clear, legally guaranteed good practice – a requirement to inform whether something was co-created with AI, generated entirely by AI or made solely by a human. (IDI #19)

Some creators also referred directly to the ethical principles underpinning AI use.

I'd really like everyone to create according to their conscience and within ethical boundaries. If they must use AI, they should do so as ethically as possible. That's all. [...] There are a lot of voices saying it's no longer worth entering the creative industry or studying for it. I disagree. In the long run, AI won't be able to replace genuine, individual creativity. (IDI #7)

Complementary to these efforts and the cultivation of responsible attitudes is the education of creators in ethics and copyright in the context of AI. In an era of automation, the human factor – integrity, judgement, and critical thinking – is of growing importance. Legal uncertainty is closely intertwined with ethical dilemmas. Participants in our workshops called for the development of ‘golden rules’ governing responsible use and stressed the need for transparency. Simply admitting to the use of AI remains crucial, though still rare, owing to public criticism and reputational concerns. Additional anxieties relate to the origins of training data and the tendency of AI systems to ‘hallucinate’, or generate false information, forcing users to verify every source manually. This legal and ethical uncertainty makes many creators cautious about deploying AI in high-stakes projects, such as music synchronisation for film.

Skills Needed for AI Implementation

Effective integration of artificial intelligence into the creative sectors requires the development of a comprehensive and multidimensional set of competencies aimed at strategically supporting and expanding human creativity – not replacing it. In Poland, as in other European countries, there is a clear demand for the development of such skills, responding to the technological transformation reshaping the industry.

What’s missing? You know what I think? Honestly – everything. There’s a lack of solid, trustworthy knowledge from reliable sources, without the panic that I see spreading throughout creative communities. We must remember that these are often highly sensitive individuals. Creators differ greatly. Some are designers from branding studios with professional managers, project leads and AI specialists, while others are single artists operating closer to the realm

of art than applied design. Their relationship to their own work and level of expertise are completely different, so it's difficult to generalise. (IDI #19)

At present, there is a shortage of appropriate training opportunities, and creators often rely on personal curiosity and experimentation:

I'm a very curious person who likes to experiment, so when this tool appeared, I started using it straight away. 95% of what I know comes from self-learning through trial and error. The remaining 5% I've picked up from YouTube or Twitter – from people showing what they've done or demonstrating new functionalities. But above all, it's about experimenting, experimenting and once again experimenting. (IDI #18)

Technical and tool-related skills are becoming fundamental. Proficiency across a wide range of generative models is increasingly essential – from text-based tools such as ChatGPT, to image generators like DALL-E, Midjourney or AI-based functions integrated with Adobe Photoshop, as well as video and audio platforms such as Runway or AudioCraft. For professionals, a deeper understanding of machine learning and AI research, combined with programming knowledge (for example, in Python), is growing in importance. Equally crucial is an understanding of data management – the 'fuel' of AI models – and familiarity with the underlying technological infrastructure, including cloud platforms and APIs^{82, 83}.

82 API – Application Programming Interface is a collection of rules, definitions and protocols which allow various programmes to communicate with each other and exchange information in a specified way.

83 Digital Poland, *State of Warsaw AI 2024*, <https://digitalpoland.org/publikacje/pobierz?id=97f8540e-d00d-48a4-a9ff-7b41d7d2d974> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

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At the same time, as participants in the workshops observed, practical experiences with tools such as Midjourney, ChatGPT, Suno and ElevenLabs vary widely. Among the successes they highlighted were time and cost savings, for instance, creating website modules independently without needing to hire a programmer. AI also effectively supports creative inspiration, automates repetitive or technical tasks such as cleaning up audio dialogue, and even enables the production of goods ‘invisible’ for the clients, such as clothing sold solely through generated images. However, failures are just as common. Users frequently complain about the low quality of free tools, lack of stylistic consistency, generation of unwanted elements and “shallow or over the top clichéd” text outputs. AI often fails to grasp artistic intent, for example when a concert poster ends up looking more like advertisement for a horror movie. Moreover, the need to fact-check AI-generated content can paradoxically make workflows longer rather than save time.

Technical proficiency alone is not enough without strong creative and conceptual skills. While algorithms can produce vast numbers of ideas, they cannot critically evaluate them. It is the human creator who must act as the supervisor and curator of the process, verifying originality and quality, and avoiding the pitfalls of homogenisation and stereotype replication⁸⁴. Developing critical thinking therefore emerges as one of the most vital areas for growth, particularly (but not solely) among younger generations of creators.

What matters to me is how students approach the topic, because I get the impression that we tend to ask artists and designers how they use artificial intelligence, but young people are much more sceptical about it. I've noticed that it's mostly people of my own generation who use AI – they're the ones really into it, while young-

84 Sabrina Habib et. al., *How does generative artificial intelligence impact student creativity?*, “Journal of Creativity” 2024, Vol. 34, Is. 1, 100072, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjoc.2023.100072>.

er people seem much less enthusiastic. [...] Still, their scepticism doesn't necessarily come from the fact that it's AI. Even before these tools became so common, I'd noticed they already struggled to find information on Google. So it's not that they've turned away from technology or decided to live more ascetically – they still use it to communicate, watch loads of videos, and listen to music. But when it comes to using it creatively, they struggle. When you give them a task, they ask how to find things or where to start. They even seem to have trouble with searching itself, with creatively connecting facts, making decisions or just trying to give things a go. (IDI #13)

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Human intentionality, unconventional thinking and the ability to ask “what if?” questions remain distinctive strengths that set genuine creativity apart from automated data processing⁸⁵. The designer's role is increasingly evolving into that of a strategist, someone who consciously selects and integrates AI-generated outcomes, shaping them into final, intended results⁸⁶.

The new market realities demand solid business competencies more than ever before. Graduates of creative disciplines frequently point to gaps in areas such as marketing, negotiation and sales. Skills in data analysis, strategic positioning of design in negotiations with business partners and knowledge of foreign markets have become essential for scaling creative activities and competing globally⁸⁷.

Complementing these are soft and interpersonal skills. Although AI encourages increasingly individualised modes of work, collaboration and communication within teams remain critical. The rapidly evolving technological environment requires a mindset of continuous learning and adaptation, as demon-

85 Francisco Tigre Moura, Chiara Castrucci, Clare Hindley, *Artificial Intelligence Creates Art?...*, op. cit.

86 Öztaş Yunus Emre, Arda Balca, *Re-evaluating creative labor...*, op. cit.

87 Centrum Rozwoju Przemysłów Kreatywnych, *Zaprojektować polski design...*, op. cit.

strated by the fact that 72% of design professionals regularly expand their knowledge⁸⁸. Equally important is interdisciplinary thinking, which connects expertise across technology, law, business and psychology.

These challenges are particularly visible in Poland, where 53% of design professionals identify artificial intelligence as the most desired area of training⁸⁹. This statistic highlights a clear gap in formal education, with universities struggling to keep pace with industry developments. Given these shortcomings, adapting educational programmes to prepare future professionals for working effectively in the AI era has become imperative.

Navigating the new technological landscape effectively and responsibly requires a fundamental reorientation of professional competencies and a systemic reform of education. Experts and practitioners highlight three key skill areas that will determine success in the age of AI. First of all, a dialogue with AI – the ability to formulate precise and creative prompts (prompt engineering) and to conduct iterative exchange with the machine to achieve desired outcomes. Second, domain expertise (or more simply, practical know-how) – paradoxically, the more powerful AI tools become, the more essential solid human knowledge becomes in terms of composition, colour theory, narrative structure or harmony. Such expertise allows for conscious direction of the process and critical evaluation of its results. And finally, critical verification – a continually refined ability to avoid accepting AI outputs uncritically, ensuring careful editing, verification and adaptation in line with one's artistic intent and quality standards.

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88 Ibid.

88 Ibid., p. 66.

Current art and design education systems remain largely unprepared for these challenges. Urgent curriculum reform is required, introducing interdisciplinary modules that cover not only digital proficiency but also AI ethics, intellectual property law and entrepreneurship in the new economy. Promoting lifelong learning and strengthening collaboration between academia and industry will be essential to ensure educational relevance in the years ahead.

The Future and Role of Creators

In the coming decade, two divergent, yet potentially coexisting, development scenarios can be surmised.

In the industrialisation scenario, AI becomes a tool for further cost optimisation in business models oriented towards mass production (e.g. fast fashion or mobile games). This could result in greater commodification of creative content and the marginalisation of individual designers in favour of centrally managed generative systems.

Alternatively, a counter-movement may emerge, driven by oversaturation with AI-generated, generic content, leading to a growing demand for unique, authentic works marked by human craftsmanship, personal narrative and materiality. In this scenario, shared by several interviewees, human-made creativity becomes a luxury good, and the label “human-made” gains both symbolic and market value.

I think that in our field, when someone hires a designer, it's because they want something individual, not something run-of-the-mill. If you want run-of-the-mill, you can do it yourself or go to a discount shop. So yes, some areas of the market might get pushed out. [...] So there'll probably be people willing to go for something like that –

just like those who buy ready-made house designs these days. But I believe there will always be clients who want a designer precisely because they're looking for something individual and someone who will guide them through the process. (IDI #21)

A likely direction for AI's evolution is a shift in the creator's role towards that of an AI conductor – a strategic visionary who manages human-machine teams, defines objectives precisely, curates and selects generated outputs, and, crucially, assumes full ethical and artistic responsibility for the final product. New professional titles such as "AI Product Designer" are already emerging, signalling a deeper restructuring of the creative professions.

It depends on the type of creative work we're talking about. I have no illusions – the most routine tasks done by graphic designers will be fully automated within a few years, maybe even sooner than five. I've no doubt about that. But design as a process is more than just what happens on a computer screen. I don't believe artificial intelligence can replace good ideas and creative thinking. It will rather support the creative process in areas where those things aren't the key factor. Being an artist, working in the field of high art, will remain part of the creative sector. And as for my own industry, I'm certain we'll see entirely new forms of advertising, things we can't even imagine today. (IDI #22)

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AI Tools Used in the Creative Sectors

In our interviews with experts and practitioners from the creative industries, participants frequently discussed their use of various AI tools. We were interested not only in which tools they used, but also why (whether to support the creative process itself or to organise their work). The list below is by no means exhaustive and will almost certainly become outdated quickly, but it aims to serve as inspiration and a practical starting point for creators seeking to integrate AI into their workflow to the extent they choose.

Music and Audio Creation Tools:

- [Meta's AudioCraft](#): a platform described as "ChatGPT for musicians," enabling text-based music generation.
- Prompt-to-song generators, e.g. [Suno](#): AI tools capable of creating full songs from text descriptions.
- AI tools for musical ideation, mastering, editing and postproduction, e.g. [eMastered](#): a broad category of AI systems supporting various stages of music creation and processing.
- [Soundlabs AI](#): technology for advanced work with vocal tracks.
- [PlayHT](#), [ElevenLabs](#): provides advanced text-to-speech (TTS) and AI voice generation services, including custom voices and pronunciations.
- [AutoPod](#): an automated video and podcast editing tool that speeds up workflows such as cutting, shot switching, video resizing, and automatic sound mixing; integrates with professional editing software.

Image and Video Creation Tools:

- [DALL-E](#): a generative AI model developed by OpenAI for creating images.
- [Stable Diffusion](#): another generative AI model for image creation.
- [Midjourney](#): a generative AI system that creates images from text prompts.
- [DeepArt AI](#): an application that transforms photos into artworks in the style of famous artists, such as Kandinsky.
- AI tools for music video creation, e.g. [Artlist.io](#).
- Sony Immersive Music Studios (Sony IMS)⁹⁰: employs motion-capture technology for creating virtual performances.

Text Generation and General Creative Support Tools:

- [ChatGPT](#): a popular AI language model used to generate text, including film and game scripts.
- [Novelcrafter](#): an AI writing platform integrating various models (GPT-3, GPT-4, Claude) to help generate plots, develop characters and create text summaries.
- [Squibbler](#): an AI-based writing assistant that generates real-time suggestions and improves grammar and style.

90 Murray Stassen, *Sony Music unveils 'next generation immersive music experiences' for Fortnite and Roblox*, <https://www.musicbusinessworldwide.com/sony-music-unveils-next-generation-immersive-music-experiences-for-fortnite-and-roblox-at-ces-in-las-vegas/> [accessed on: 07/10/2025].

- [Sudowrite](#): an AI assistant for creative writing, helping with ideation, story development and narrative design.
- [Bielik.ai](#): a Polish language model developed at AGH University of Science and Technology in Kraków; designed for dialogue, answering questions and generating diverse texts, including poetry and fiction.
- [Adobe](#) products, including [Adobe Photoshop](#) with integrated AI tools: a widely used graphic design software incorporating AI-powered functions to support creative workflows.

Recommendations

Clear Legal Frameworks

Implementing **copyright and digital market regulations is only half the battle. Ongoing analysis of emerging areas of exploitation is vital to prevent the further expansion of the “grey zone”** in AI use across the creative industries. Equally important is the development of effective mechanisms to ensure these rules can be properly enforced. Precise legal provisions are needed to govern the use of AI tools, particularly in relation to intellectual property protection within digital design and UX (User Experience), so that creators are not left to rely on vague or overly general standards. Solutions should empower creators to make informed decisions about managing their intellectual property, both when consenting to the use of their works for model training and when co-creating content with generative AI. This process should be accompanied by educational initiatives (outlined below) to ensure that the new legal frameworks are not only adopted but also clearly understood by those they are intended to protect. Such measures would enable creators to actively prevent the unauthorised use of their work for algorithm training.

Transparency and Accountability

It is essential to introduce measures that strengthen transparency of AI solutions. These should include an obligation to maintain and disclose **registers of copyrighted materials** used in model training. In addition, any content generated, in whole or in part, by AI should be **clearly labelled**. Such measures would give audiences greater clarity and allow consumers to consciously recognise and value authentic, human creativity.

Reducing Bias in AI Models

Training data can introduce and perpetuate **bias and discrimination** within AI models. The problem, rooted in earlier datasets like WordNet and ImageNet, requires proactive mitigation. Efforts should focus on developing and applying ethical AI tools, alongside ensuring **diversity and representativeness** in training datasets to prevent the reproduction of harmful stereotypes.

Supporting Human Creativity and Uniqueness

Despite AI's vast potential, there are legitimate concerns about **homogenisation and the loss of individuality** in creative work, resulting in "flat" and uninspired outcomes. It is therefore crucial to promote AI as **a tool that supports, rather than replaces, human creativity**. In response to the overproduction of mass-generated content, the value of originality and the "human touch" in art and design should be reasserted.

The **promotion and protection of authorship** should be reinforced through the active support and showcasing of unique human craftsmanship. Certification mechanisms or labels (such as "Created by Human") could help audiences make more informed choices.

Educational Support and Skills Development

Rapid technological change calls for a thorough revision of higher education curricula. Legal, ethical, business, and technological topics, ideally taught by industry practitioners, should be integrated to better prepare future creators for the realities of the market. The strong demand for AI-related training (reported by 53% of respondents) highlights the urgent need to **address systemic knowledge gaps**. Educational programmes must equip students with the ability to use AI tools both effectively and responsibly, covering their technical as well as ethical dimensions.

Cross-Sector Dialogue and Collaboration

Effective implementation of change requires broad collaboration. It is recommended to organise **roundtables** bringing together representatives of the creative industries and public institutions **to jointly identify barriers and optimise support programmes**. A partnership-based dialogue between designers and entrepreneurs, with the support of public institutions, can help strengthen the role of design in the economy, accelerate the effective transfer of innovation and encourage responsible use of technology within creative processes.

Principles for Responsible AI Use

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Based on the findings of this study, we propose an open, preliminary set of principles to guide responsible AI use in creative practice, along with key questions to consider before integrating AI into the creative process.

- 1. Transparency and traceability** – always clearly communicate when content has been generated or significantly modified by AI. Whenever possible, use tools that disclose the sources of their training data.
- 2. Copyright protection** – ensure that your use of AI tools does not infringe your own or others' intellectual property rights. Choose platforms that rely on legally and ethically sourced datasets.
- 3. Human-centred approach** – treat AI as a supportive tool rather than a substitute for human creativity, critical thinking and judgement. Ultimate responsibility for the work always rests with you.
- 4. Awareness of bias** – be aware that AI models may reproduce and amplify existing stereotypes. Critically assess outputs for potential bias and work to minimise it in your creative practice.
- 5. Continuous learning** – actively expand your knowledge of the tools you use and their ethical implications. Technology develops rapidly, and responsible use requires a commitment to ongoing education.

Before using AI in your project, ask yourself:

- 1. Purpose:** What specific problem do I want to solve using AI? Will it enhance my creative process or merely automate it (bearing in mind the risk of losing originality)? Or do I intend to use AI for operational tasks that support creative work?
- 2. Data and copyright:** Do I know what data the model was trained on? Is its use legal and compliant with intellectual property rights? Do I know what will happen to my own data or works when I use the tool?
- 3. Transparency:** Will my audience, clients or collaborators know to what extent AI was used in this project? How will I communicate that?
- 4. Control and added value:** Am I maintaining full creative control over the final outcome? Does AI make the result better or simply more generic?
- 5. Bias:** What potential stereotypes or biases could the tool introduce? How can I identify and correct them?
- 6. Competence:** Do I and my team have sufficient knowledge to use this tool consciously, critically and effectively?

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Appendices

Appendix 1.

Expert In-Depth Interview Scenario

Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Creative Industries

Introduction

Hello and thank you very much for taking the time to speak with me. This interview concerns the role and impact of artificial intelligence within the creative sectors of architecture, design, fashion, music and video games. I'm interested in your experiences, observations, and opinions regarding current and potential future uses of AI in creative work. The interview is of a research nature and will be used for academic purposes. For this reason, the interview will be recorded. Anonymised quotations may be included in the research report. [Ask for consent to record and to use anonymised quotes.]

I. Professional background

1. Could you briefly describe your professional activity within the creative sector?

- Which areas of creative work do you represent?
- What are you currently working on?
- How long have you been active in this field?

II. Current use of AI

2. Do you currently use artificial intelligence in your work?

If so, how?

- Which AI tools do you use (e.g. image generators, text generators, editing tools, data analysis tools)?
- Does AI support your creative process, or is it used more in organisational / production or research and preparatory stages? [It is important to map the areas of AI use accurately.]

3. Do you know of other individuals or teams in your field who actively use AI? What are their practices? How would you assess the overall level of AI adoption among creators in your field?

- Examples of projects involving the use of AI?
- Examples of good and bad applications of AI?

III. Attitudes and perceptions of creators toward AI

4. How do you personally feel about the growing presence of AI in creative professions? Do you see it more as an opportunity or a threat? Why? [It's worth asking about both.]

5. How does your creative community respond to AI tools?

Is there enthusiasm, scepticism or concern? Why?

IV. Intellectual property and authorship

6. Do you see any challenges related to intellectual property in the context of AI?

- Who is the author of a work co-created with AI?
- In your professional network, are there concerns about copying, inspiration or “fair use”?

7. Do you think the use of AI changes the very definition of creativity? How do you perceive it?

V. Competence and preparedness of creators

8. Do you think creators are adequately prepared to work with AI?

- What skills are necessary for this?
- What kind of education or training do you think is needed?

9. Have you personally had an opportunity to develop AI-related skills? If so, how?

VI. The future of AI in the creative sectors

10. How do you imagine the future use of AI in your field?

- What changes might occur over the next 5–10 years?
- Do you think creative work will become more automated, or will entirely new forms of expression emerge?

11. What conditions need to be in place for AI to support, rather than threaten, creators?

Conclusion

12. Is there anything else you would like to add, anything we haven't discussed, that you consider important in the context of AI and creativity?

[Thank the participant for their time.]

Appendix 2.

Quantitative Survey Questionnaire

Please note: the quantitative survey questionnaire was only available to the respondents in its original Polish language, and the following translation was made for the purpose of this report.

Creative Industries and the Development of Artificial Intelligence (AI)

We invite you to take part in a survey exploring how artificial intelligence tools are transforming the functioning of Poland's creative industries.

The survey is part of the research project "CRE-AI-TIVE: Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Creative Industries". The aim of the project is to analyse how new AI-driven tools and applications are revolutionising the fields of architecture, design, fashion, music and video games, as well as how creators approach the use of AI in their work. Completing the survey will take no more than 10 minutes. Your opinions are crucial to gaining an accurate picture of contemporary creative communities. The survey is anonymous, and all collected data will be processed in aggregate form.

Thank you for your time!

Co-financed by the Minister of Culture and National Heritage under the Creative Industries Development Centre's own programme: "Rozwój Sektorów Kreatywnych".

More about the project: <https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/projekty/cre-ai-tive-badanie-wykorzystania-sztucznej-inteligencji-w-przemyslach-kreatywnych/>

For questions or to participate in the in-depth interviews, please contact us at: kontakt@centrumcyfrowe.pl

Privacy Policy: <https://centrumcyfrowe.pl/polityka-prywatnosci/>

1. Which sector do you represent? (Selecting “Other” ends the survey.)

- Architecture
- Games
- Fashion
- Music
- Product/Industrial Design
- Other

2. Gender

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary person
- Prefer not to say

3. Education

- Primary
- Secondary
- Higher
- Currently studying a field related to design, fashion, music, architecture or video games

4. Professional experience in your sector

- I am a student
- Less than 3 years
- 3-5 years
- 6-10 years
- 11-15 years
- 16-20 years
- More than 20 years

5. Type of professional activity

- Self-employed (sole proprietorship or partnership)
- Employed under a contract of employment, contract for the provision of services or specific work (as a natural person)
- Non-profit activity (in a foundation or association)
- Unregistered business activity
- Not yet professionally active

6. Form of business activity

- Independent, not employing others
- Company employing up to 9 people (microenterprise)
- Company employing 10–50 people (small enterprise)
- Company employing 51–250 people (medium-sized enterprise)
- Company employing more than 250 people (large enterprise)
- Non-governmental organisation (NGO)

7. Type of organisation in which you are employed (under an employment contract, contract for the provision of services or specific work)

- Company employing up to 9 people (microenterprise)
- Company employing 10–50 people (small enterprise)
- Company employing 51–250 people (medium-sized enterprise)
- Company employing more than 250 people (large enterprise)
- Non-governmental organisation (NGO)

8. At which stage of your work (creation, production, sales, etc.) do you use AI-based tools?

- Project preparation and research
- Creative work (creating the work, generating concepts and variants)
- Organisation and administration
- Promotion and communication
- I do not use AI-based tools

9. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I am open to the possibility of using AI in my creative work					
I am aware that AI-based tools are being used within my team					
I try not to think about new issues related to AI					
I am afraid of the introduction of new AI-based tools					
AI only optimises processes, but does not affect the creative layer of the work					
The use of AI has a negative impact on the quality of the final work					
AI-based tools are still too underdeveloped to have a positive effect on the quality of creative output					
The use of AI in creative work should be clearly labelled and described					

10. What risks do you see in connection with the use of artificial intelligence?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Dependence on technology – over-reliance on AI may lead to loss of human skills and knowledge					
Bias and discrimination – AI can inherit existing biases from training data, leading to discrimination and unfair decisions					
Privacy risks – AI often requires large amounts of data for training and operation, raising concerns about privacy and data security					
Lack of a “human factor” – AI can be efficient but lacks emotional engagement (e.g. empathy, understanding, awareness of micro-aggressions) that is crucial in many professions that require emotional awareness					
Job losses – automation of creative processes may reduce the number of roles					
Decline of human creativity – reliance on generative AI limits creators’ own creativity (automation of imagination, loss of individual artistic voice)					

11. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
Using AI-based tools signifi cantly accelerates creative work					
Using AI-based tools reduces costs associated with creative work					
Using AI-based tools improves management and organisation of work					
Using AI-based tools enables visual effects that were previously hard to achieve					
Using AI-based tools allows for faster and better data analysis					

12. In your opinion, what challenges related to AI does your industry currently face?

	Not at all	To a small extent	No opinion	To some extent	To a large extent
The threat to the existence of my profession (loss of jobs)					
Lack of suffi cient skills to use AI-based tools					
Inadequate protection of creators' copyrights (uncontrolled use of our work by AI)					
The widespread use of AI leading to a decline in the quality (originality) of fi nal creative works					

13. Can you think of any other important challenges, particularly related to AI, that your industry is currently facing? (open-ended question)

14. In your opinion, what will be the biggest AI-related challenges your industry will face in the future?

	Not at all	To a small extent	No opinion	To some extent	To a large extent
Dehumanisation of cultural expression (art ceases to reflect human emotions, experiences and perspectives)					
Decline in creative skills among creators (dependence on AI tools may discourage skill development and experimentation)					
Ethical dilemmas (AI may generate deepfakes, plagiarism or art that reinforces harmful social narratives)					
Unequal access to advanced AI tools (independent creators and small studios may become marginalised)					
Loss of jobs in creative professions (automation of creative processes)					

	Not at all	To a small extent	No opinion	To some extent	To a large extent
Issues related to copyright and intellectual property (diffi culty in determining authorship, infringement of creators' rights)					
Standardisation and homogenisation of creativity (AI generates content based on existing works, risking the "averaging out" of aesthetics)					

15. Can you think of any other important challenges, particularly related to AI, that your industry might face in the future? (open-ended question)

Thank you for taking part in the survey!

Would you like to stay up to date with our project? You are welcome to subscribe to the Centrum Cyfrowe newsletter:

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About the Report

Abstract

The report “CRE-AI-TIVE. Creatives in the Age of AI” analyses the impact of artificial intelligence on the design, fashion, architecture, music and video game industries in Poland. Based on extensive desk research, 23 in-depth interviews with representatives of the creative sectors and a quantitative survey, the study reveals the dual nature of AI: on the one hand, as a catalyst for innovation that is transforming creative processes and business models; on the other, as a source of significant legal, ethical and economic challenges.

The majority of Polish creators (86%) already use AI tools, primarily to optimise and accelerate their work. AI is widely viewed as a partner in the creative process, supporting idea generation and prototyping. At the same time, however, artists express serious concerns about the unauthorised use of their works for model training, which has created a legal “grey area”. Other risks include cultural homogenisation, job losses (particularly in entry-level positions), a shortage of relevant skills and the absence, or limited awareness, of legal frameworks designed to safeguard the creative industries.

The report underscores the urgent need to refine existing legal frameworks and establish clear ethical guidelines to ensure transparency and the effective protection of intellectual property. Key recommendations include developing educational programmes, supporting human creativity and promoting cross-sector dialogue. The report also calls for the mandatory labelling of AI-generated content and the disclosure of training datasets by technology companies. We argue that a strategic and responsible approach to AI will enable Poland’s creative sectors to fully harness the potential of this transformative technology.

Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation

The Centrum Cyfrowe Foundation is a think-and-do tank committed to ensuring that new technologies serve the public good. Its work focuses on the digital dimension of public life in Poland, specifically on analysing the social, cultural, and economic changes brought about by digital technologies. This goes hand in hand with our commitment to advancing knowledge in this area. We promote openness in knowledge and cultural institutions and work towards social change by using digital tools and collaborative models based on sharing resources and expertise.

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